

Surgical Management of Persistent Oroantral Communication: A Case Report

Author: Emanuela Vreme¹

Coordinator: Cristian Budacu ¹

Affiliations:

¹ *Aesthetica Clinic*

Introduction

Oroantral communication (OAC) is a common complication following extraction of posterior maxillary teeth and represents a significant etiological factor in odontogenic maxillary sinusitis. Persistent OAC permits contamination of the maxillary sinus, leading to chronic inflammation. Early diagnosis and appropriate surgical management are essential to prevent long-term morbidity and restore normal sinus function.

Case Presentation

A 53-year-old male patient presented with unilateral nasal discharge, halitosis, and regurgitation of fluids from the oral cavity into the nasal passage following extraction of the maxillary left first molar (2.6) in November 2025. Clinical examination revealed a persistent left oroantral communication. Computed tomography confirmed the presence of the defect, along with mucosal thickening and partial opacification of the maxillary sinus, consistent with chronic sinusitis. Surgical management involved closure of the defect using a buccal advancement flap. Prior to flap placement, the sinus cavity was irrigated and debrided. The flap was then mobilized and advanced to achieve tension-free closure. Postoperative management included systemic antibiotics, nasal decongestants, and sinus precautions. Healing was uneventful, with successful closure of the communication and complete resolution of sinus-related symptoms. No recurrence or complications were observed during follow-up.

Conclusion

Chronic maxillary sinusitis secondary to oroantral communication requires prompt and effective management. The buccal advancement flap remains a simple, reliable, and predictable technique for closure of appropriately selected oroantral communications.

Keywords

Oroantral communication; maxillary sinusitis; buccal advancement flap; odontogenic infection; oral surgery